

Quantum chemical computation of localized orbitals of some simple chemical systems

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The orbital hybridization and bonding in the diatomic systems, viz. N_2 , $(NO)^-$, $(NO)^+$, CO and $(CN)^-$ have been computed through the Localized Molecular Orbitals. Results show that although the bonding in the molecules looks similar to qualitative structure theory, the hybridizations in the atoms are much different from those of qualitative theory.

The simple diatomic molecular species like N_2 , CO, $(NO)^+$, $(NO)^-$ and $(CN)^-$ are widely known both experimentally and theoretically. These are also known to form large number of coordination complexes with metals and metal analogues like BH_3 and BF_3 . For an understanding and correlating chemistry of such molecules the knowledge of their electronic structure is important. The valence bond structures of the molecules are drawn on the assumption that s and p orbitals hybridize in a same sp way on each atom. Pauling hybridization scheme¹ is unable to incorporate the response concomitant to the change of the environment of the atom. There is no hybridization in the MO theory and the Hartree-Fock-Roothaan² method generates MO's which are fully delocalized and called Canonical Molecular Orbitals (CMO's) or Spectroscopic Molecular Orbitals (SMO's)³. The CMO's immensely help spectroscopic studies but the conceptual chemistry of bond-pairs and lone-pairs vanishes in such quantum chemical method. Fukui⁴ suggested a method, adapted by Ghosh⁵ in a simpler form, especially suited to study complexes formed by BH_3 and molecules under study. But this method too falls within the paradigm of MO theory. A number of experimental studies⁶ reveals unequivocally that hybridization is a reality in such molecules. It was discovered that the set of CMO's or SMO's is one of the many possible unitary bases in Hartree-Fock space and new sets of MO's which conform to chemical intuition in terms of lone-pairs and bond-pairs can be generated by suitable unitary transformation in the same Hartree-Fock space. Such MO's are called Localized Molecular Orbitals (LMO's). Such LMO's provide the lone-pairs and bond-pairs in a non-arbitrary mathematical way. Of the suggested models of Localization^{7,8}, the method of Sinanoğlu⁸ furnishes LMO's which offer a framework for computing hybridization quantitatively. The method is very fast and maintains the σ - π separation. Therefore, we have taken up the present study of generating LMO's of each of the molecular species for computing quantitative hybridization and discussing bonding.

In the experimental, Canonical Molecular Orbitals (CMO's) of each of the molecular species are generated by

CNDO/2 method of Pople⁹ and co-workers at their optimized geometries. The CMO's are then transformed into LMO's by the method of Sinanoğlu⁸ and then we have proceeded to discuss the bonding and hybridization in terms of the LMO's.

Results and Discussion

(i) Dinitrogen (N_2) :

The chemical inertness of N_2 is well known although it functions as coordinating ligand. The LMO's of dinitrogen molecule is shown in Table 1 which reveals that there are effectively three bonds, one σ -type and two π -type, between the atoms and there is one lone-pair on each atom. The electronic structure can be written as $:N\equiv N:$. The computed hybridization, in terms of the LMO's, shows that nitrogen atoms use $sp^{2.8}$ hybrid orbitals to form the σ -bond and the hybridization in the lone-pairs is $s^{2.8}p$. The lone-pairs in atoms, being $s^{2.8}p$ hybrid, are more deep seated and is less polarizable and available for chemical response. Thus the extreme inertness of the molecule is revealing through the present calculation.

Table 1. Localized molecular orbitals (LMO's) of N_2

LMO's A.O.'s ↓	$\rightarrow 1.p.(1N)$	$1.p.(2N)$	$\sigma(N-N)$	$\pi(px-px)$	$\pi(py-py)$
1N2s	0.8602	-0.0000	-0.3605	0.0000	0.0000
1N2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.7071	0.0000
1N2py	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.7071
1N2pz	-0.5098	0.0000	-0.6083	0.0000	0.0000
2N2s	-0.0000	0.8602	-0.3605	0.0000	0.0000
2N2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.7071	0.0000
2N2py	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.7071
2N2pz	0.0000	0.5098	0.6083	0.0000	0.0000

(ii) Nitric oxide anion, $(NO)^-$ and nitrosonium cation, $(NO)^+$:

The LMO's of $(NO)^-$ and $(NO)^+$ are shown in Tables 2 and 3 respectively. From Table 2 it is evident that there are two chemical bonds, one σ -type and the other π -type, be-

tween N and O and two lone-pairs of electrons on each N and O of $(\text{NO})^-$. One lone-pair is purely p -type in both N and O atoms. The other one is s^4p hybrid on N and $s^{3.6}p$ on O. Thus the lone-pairs on both the atoms are similar in mode of hybridization and more available for coordination. It is an experimental fact that $(\text{NO})^-$ is a good donor. To form the σ -bond, the N atom provides $sp^{4.2}$ hybrid while the O atom provides $sp^{3.6}$ hybrid. From Table 3 it is evident that in $(\text{NO})^+$, there are three chemical bonds, one σ -type and other two π -types, between the atoms and there is one lone-pair on each N and O atoms. The lone-pair on N is $s^{2.9}p$ and that on O is $s^{2.2}p$. The positive charge together with the mode of hybridization of lone-pairs make the $(\text{NO})^+$ system a bad donor. The σ -bond between the atoms is formed by a $sp^{2.9}$ hybrid of N atom and $sp^{2.2}$ hybrid of O atom. From the above discussion, the electronic structure of the molecules can be depicted as $(:\ddot{\text{N}}=\ddot{\text{O}}:)^-$, and $(:\text{N}\equiv\text{O}:)^+$ which is in fact a reproduction of classical structure. It is further noted that to form σ -bond in both molecules, N atom provides hybrid orbitals with higher p -character than that of O. Since O is more electronegative than N, this type of hybridization is quite expected in terms of Bent's rule¹⁰.

Table 2. Localized molecular orbitals (LMO'S) of $(\text{NO})^-$

L.M.O.'s $\rightarrow \sigma(\text{N-O})$ A.O.'s	11.p.(N)	21.p.(N)	11.p.(O)	$\pi(px-px)$	21.p.(O)
\downarrow					
N2s	0.2981	0.8992	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000
N2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.5404
N2py	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	0.0000	0.0000
N2pz	0.6127	-0.4376	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000
O2s	0.3402	-0.0000	0.0000	0.8854	0.0000
O2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.8414
O2py	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-1.0000
O2pz	-0.6480	-0.0000	0.0000	0.4648	0.0000

Table 3. Localized molecular orbitals (LMO'S) of $(\text{NO})^+$

L.M.O.'s $\rightarrow \sigma(\text{N-O})$ A.O.'s	1.p.(N)	$\pi(px-px)$	$\pi(py-py)$	1.p.(O)
\downarrow				
N2s	0.3356	0.8641	0.0000	-0.0000
N2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.6109	0.0000
N2py	0.0000	0.0000	0.6109	0.0000
N2pz	0.5762	-0.5033	0.0000	-0.0000
O2s	0.4142	-0.0000	0.0000	0.8313
O2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.7916	0.0000
O2py	0.0000	0.0000	0.7916	0.0000
O2pz	-0.6195	-0.0000	0.0000	0.5558

(iii) Carbon monoxide, CO :

CO is an exceedingly weak Lewis base but still it acts as an important donor ligand. From Table 4 it is evident that there are three bonds, one σ -type and the other two π -type, between the two atoms and there is one lone-pair on each of the atoms. The hybridization in the lone-pair of C atom is $s^{3.4}p$ and that in the lone-pair of O atom is $s^{2.2}p$. The σ -bond between the C and O is formed by overlap of $sp^{3.4}$

hybrid of C and sp^2 hybrid of O. The lone-pair of C, being a $s^{3.4}p$ hybrid, should be insensitive towards a chemical response. The hybrid of C (a less electronegative atom) forming σ -bond with O (a more electronegative atom) has higher p -character in due compliance to the Bent's rule¹⁰.

Table 4. Localized molecular orbitals (LMO'S) of CO

L.M.O.'s $\rightarrow s(\text{C-O})$ A.O.'s	1.p.(C)	$\pi(px-px)$	$\pi(py-py)$	1.p.(O)
\downarrow				
C2s	0.3029	0.8783	0.0000	0.0000
C2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.5270	0.0000
C2py	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.5270
C2pz	0.5566	-0.4780	0.0000	0.0000
O2s	0.4449	0.0000	0.0000	0.8180
O2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.8498	0.0000
O2py	0.0000	0.0000	0.8498	0.0000
O2pz	-0.6327	-0.0000	0.0000	0.5752

(iv) The $(\text{CN})^-$, unlike CO, can attach itself through both C and N atoms to form cyanide and isocyanide complexes. The LMO's, shown in Table 5 demonstrates that $(\text{CN})^-$ is triple bonded, one bond is σ and other two are π -types. There is one lone-pair on C and another one on N. Thus the electronic structure of $(\text{CN})^-$ can be written as $(:\text{C}\equiv\text{N}:)^-$. The lone-pair on C atom is $s^{2.4}p$ hybrid and that on N is $s^{1.7}p$ hybrid. The σ -bond between C and N is formed by overlap of a $sp^{2.4}$ hybrid of C with $sp^{1.7}$ hybrid of N. Thus more electronegative atom N polarizes p -electrons more in the neighbouring atom C to form σ -bond in conformity with Bent's rule¹⁰.

Table 5. Localized molecular orbitals (LMO'S) of $(\text{CN})^-$

L.M.O.'s $\rightarrow \sigma(\text{C-N})$ A.O.'s	1.p.(C)	$\pi(px-px)$	$\pi(py-py)$	1.p.(N)
\downarrow				
C2s	0.3646	0.8396	0.0000	0.0000
C2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.6465	0.0000
C2py	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.6465
C2pz	0.5635	-0.5432	0.0000	0.0000
N2s	0.4465	-0.0000	0.0000	0.7983
N2px	0.0000	0.0000	0.7629	0.0000
N2py	0.0000	0.0000	0.7629	0.0000
N2pz	-0.5917	-0.0000	0.0000	0.6023

From the above results of LMO's and calculation of quantitative hybridization in the series of diatomics it is very evident that (i) the present quantum chemical calculation virtually reproduces the classical valence bond structure of the molecules. (ii) The hybridization in the atoms are far from those envisaged in terms of Pauling's model. (iii) The hybridization in the lone-pairs and bond pairs on each atom are different. (iv) The hybridization in lone-pairs better correlates the chemical reactivity of the molecules. (v) In order to form the covalent bond between the hetero atom, the s and p orbitals blend on atoms in a ratio so as to

incorporate the response from the environment consistent with the Bent's rule.

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